

GENOMED4ALL

D4.1 Hybrid Federated Learning model

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

D4.1

Hybrid Federated Learning Model

Work package	WP4
Task	T4.1
Due date	31-12-2021
Submission date	27-01-2022
Deliverable lead	UPM
Version	V1
Authors	Silvia Uribe (UPM), Javier Serrano (UPM), Alberto del Río (UPM), Davide Piscia (CRG), Vincent Planant (DEDALUS)
Reviewers	DW, UNIBO

Abstract

The main aim of this deliverable is to define GenoMed4All's hybrid federated learning model specification expressed in terms of platform requirements, which have been acquired by analyzing in details the project's objectives as well as by decomposing the stakeholders' needs through the different use cases' definition. It includes a description of the requirements elicitation methodology together with the set of technical requirements regarding the federated learning approach of the project's platform. Moreover, it includes an extensive analysis of the most important federated learning framework solutions already available, and it finally defines the evaluation criteria that have helped in the selection of the most appropriate one for the project's purposes and needs.

Keywords

Federated learning framework, hybrid platform, centralized processing, federated processing, requirements, federated platform components.

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.1	04-10-2021	1 st version of ToC	Silvia Uribe (UPM)
v0.2	07-01-2022	Final version of Chapter 2 and 3	Silvia Uribe (UPM)
v0.3	10-01-2022	Final version of Chapter 4	Silvia Uribe (UPM)
V0.4	11-01-2022	Final version of Chapter 6	Davide Piscia (CRG), Alberto del Río, Javier Serrano (UPM)
V0.5	12-01-2022	Final version of Chapter 5	Vincent Planant (DEDALUS)
V0.6	13-01-2022	Conclusions and final version of Executive Summary	Silvia Uribe (UPM)
V0.7	14-01-2022	Version for revision	Gastone Castellani (UNIBO) and Francesco Cremonesi (DW)
V0.8	24-01-2022	Final version after revision	Silvia Uribe (UPM)

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme

Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to GENOMED4ALL project and Commission Services

*** Deliverable types:**

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDM	Common Data Model
CDS	Clinical Decision Support
CSV	Comma Separated Value
DoW	Description of Work
DSL	Domain Specific Language
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FL	Federated Learning
FR	Functional requirement
HPC	High Performance Computing
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
ML	Machine Learning
MM	Multiple Myeloma
NFR	Non-functional requirement
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
VPN	Virtual Private Network

1 Executive summary

GenoMed4all aims to pool genomic, clinical data and other “-omics” health data of hematological diseases for advancing research and personalized medicine. The sensitivity of such data requires relevant measures that can be properly (pseudo)anonymized and analyzed within a distributed learning system that avoids the data transferring from their original locations (due to legal constraints and other requirements from the data owners). This system will allow the generation and application of advanced AI models for precision medicine, which will be further improved with the inclusion of HPC resources as planned.

With the above goal in mind, the main aim of this deliverable is to define GenoMed4All’s hybrid federated learning model specification expressed in terms of platform requirements. The model specification has been acquired after detailed analysis of the project’s objectives as well as the needs of stakeholders obtained by studying different use cases, where the former was obtained from the GenoMed4All information in the Description of Work (DoW), while the latter can be consulted in detail in D3.2 End user requirements. In accordance, this deliverable presents the methodology implemented for the requirements gathering, which was shared with other work packages such as WP3 and WP5 with the aim to gather similar view of the entire process. Moreover, a special attention to the system capabilities and the functional and non-functional requirements has been discussed to obtain a final list to be considered in the development and deployment of the platform. The platform design model can be considered as one of the most important contributions of this document as it contains information about the initial definition and its further evolution, including the main components that will be in charge of allowing the collaboration on a shared AI learning approach, considering different use cases.

Finally, this document is also in charge of defining a set of guidelines for the platform provision based on an extended analysis of the most used solutions in the AI frameworks environment. This analysis includes a description of the principal available open-source solutions that could be of any help in this project. After this, a description of a set of initial tests over the most proper ones according to the project’s needs has helped to the selection of the one to be used in GenoMed4All federated platform: Flower Federated Learning platform¹. Nevertheless, this framework (as in the case of the other options that have been analyzed) does not include all the modules that will be needed for the different user cases provision, so an additional effort will be needed in order to create them and to complete the required functionalities. The description of these modules and the related functionalities will help the fulfillment of the other tasks in the work package.

Finally, this deliverable has been delayed for helping the improvement of Section 6, which is vital for the designing and implementation of the federated learning approach.

¹ <https://flower.dev/>

2 Introduction

The work presented in this report was completed as part of the GenoMed4All project, which will support the advance research in personalized medicine in hematological diseases based on the advance use of genomic, clinical data and other “-omics” health data for innovative AI model provision over a federated learning scheme. This deliverable belongs to WP4 that has as primary objective to define the federated learning infrastructure derived from the data sharing, provision and AI model creation defined through the different use cases which have helped to obtain a clear system specification. Within this work package, this document represents the first outcome of Task 4.1 AI federated learning mechanism design from M6 to M12, and it has been led by UPM and having as main contributors DEDALUS and CRG, although the inputs that have been considered come from the entire consortium.

This chapter can be seen as an introduction to the research undertaken in order to materialise Deliverable 4.1 of the project by introducing the motivation that has driven the analysis activities as the first ones to be done when defining an infrastructure such as this one, it includes a brief presentation of the organisation with an overview of the document structure and finally, it presents the main connections with the rest of the work packages in the project.

2.1 Purpose of the document

Due to the nature of the project, GenoMed4All is considered to be a very complex data-driven project that is integrating several components and data sources. In the context of the project, each component or module can be seen as every entity that produces explicit functionality that will be integrated in the project framework. In this sense, the main contributors for these modules will be WP5, which is mainly in charge of defining the data processing operations, composed by anonymization, curation and homogenization tools that will allow the use of the available health data according to the legal and ethics requirements, and WP6, focused on the obtaining of innovative AI algorithms for personalized medicine in the project’s context. With regards to the data sources, as explained in WP3 deliverables (especially in D3.1), there are different repositories to be considered both within the consortium and outside from EU platform and public registries for the three diseases to be contemplated.

Having in mind this, WP4 aims at providing the mechanisms and infrastructures to enable a proper linkage of -omics data and, for doing so, there are four main objectives to be fulfilled:

- ❑ To define, describe and implement the hybrid structure between federated learning and centralized learning that allows the accommodation of small and big players needs through different mechanisms and components.
- ❑ To elaborate the data sharing platform with all the modules needed for the hybrid learning.
- ❑ To define a computing distribution of the project’s infrastructure that includes high proficiency computing of AI algorithms
- ❑ To integrate, deploy and validate the previously defined infrastructure for linking different “-omics” repositories through AI.

The objectives of this WP that are relevant to this deliverable are primarily those described in the first and second of the previous list, but they are highly coupled with the other ones. Therefore, the principal aim of this deliverable can be summarized as follow: it will develop the model for AI learning, following a federated learning approach combined with a centralized one for those data which are not so privacy relevant or can be properly anonymized and based on previous experiences by the task's contributors. Accordingly, this objective implies that there is an intrinsic connection between this task and the rest of the work package, since the output of this one can be considered as a design guidance that will provide the essential information for the implementation and deployment of the GenoMed4All federated learning platform according to the main stakeholders' needs and system requirements

2.2 Structure of the document

According to the main objective of this document that is to provide an initial approach to the federated learning infrastructure, this document is divided into five main chapters. Chapter 3 is mainly focused on an initial analysis of the project through the revision of the different use cases that have been considered. Furthermore, it also includes an explanation about the need for a hybrid model which includes a combination of federated and centralised capabilities based on operational, legal and ethics constraints. Based on this analysis, Chapter 4 is in charge of providing an analysis of the technical requirements of the platform. For doing so, an introduction to the methodology that has been followed is presented, together with the requirements definition issues and negotiation with the main contributors (clinical and AI experts). Once the requirements have been presented, Chapter 5 is responsible for introducing the designing of the platform. In this regard, this chapter includes the initial definition and the evolution plan together with the description of the platform's components and main actors. Finally, Chapter 6 oversees describing the initial implementation guidelines. It includes a state of the art of the main existing federated learning framework solutions together with an initial test of those more related to the needs of the project. Moreover, it also includes the definition of the evaluation criteria for the framework selection, followed by the assessment of the main solutions and finally the reasoning behind the selection of the best option for the project: Flower FL framework. Finally, since none of the analysed options is able to provide all the capabilities needed, this chapter is closed by a section that includes an analysis of the modules to be implemented to cover all the functionalities. Conclusions are set in Chapter 7.

2.3 Linkage with other WPs

As it has been previously said, this work package is clearly connected with the rest of the work packages within GenoMed4All, and it can be considered as the spinal cord that vertebrates the entire system. Following this idea, the main linkage with other work packages is:

- With WP2: this work package is in charge of defining the legal and ethical framework for the project, which directly impacts the FL platform to be defined within WP4. Following this idea, WP2 will provide important non-functional requirements that will be vital for the validation of the system.

- ❑ With WP3: as mentioned above, the information provided by WP3 can be considered as one of the main inputs of this deliverable. In fact, the definition of the data sources and their main formats (D3.1) together with the description of the use case scenarios and users' requirements (D3.2) and finally the data model (D3.3) are vital to understand the context of the project and to derive the main technical requirements of the platform.
- ❑ With WP5: the connection with this work package is clear since, as previously said, it is responsible for the data processing that will allow the data usage within the platform by following the legal, operational and ethics requirements related to the use of health data.
- ❑ With WP6: as AI model providers, work package 6 can be considered as one of the main stakeholders of this work package. Their needs must be fulfilled in a very strict way to allow the correct operation of the algorithms, following their specific requirements. Moreover, and following the federated learning training pipeline proposed by WP6 (D6.2), connection between these three technical work packages can be clearly seen in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1. Federated learning pipeline description and technical work packages main responsibilities (extracted from D6.2). While WP5 is in charge of the data engineering and WP6 is focused on the provision of the AI models, WP4 is responsible of allowing the creation of a federated platform to help in the imputation and training phases of the model

- ❑ With WP7: as clinical contributors, the linkage with work package 7 is clear. They can be considered as the main users of the platform (together with WP6), so their requirements are

vital for a good definition of the system. Moreover, they will oversee the validation of the platform through the different use cases deployment.

- ❑ With WP8: the linkage with this work package can be seen through two different perspectives: on one hand, the standardization needs, the FAIR principles to be followed, etc., will impact directly the platform provision and its use. On the other, the training education that is part of their responsibilities is directly related to the platform, and the ease of use should be considered as a very important requirement to help in this task.
- ❑ With WP9: the contribution of this work package, especially from the implementation of additional modules to complete the selected AI framework, to the open access strategy of the project can be seen as an important initiative for the entire project.

3 Initial analysis

3.1 Need for a hybrid model: from centralized to federated learning approach

As can be seen in Fig. 2, the platform evolution suggested for the project includes two main phases, going from a centralized version capable of providing different functionalities for the AI model creation to a federated version able to improve them with the data available from additional nodes without sharing any personal data.

Fig. 2. Platform evolution approach, from a centralised architecture on phase 1 to a federated one on phase 2

The rationale behind this design decision can be clearly explained when defining the different steps needed for obtaining the distributed AI algorithms planned for GenoMed4All:

□ Step 1: Initial model development using a centralized data model:

This first step will be responsible for the design of distributed algorithms through a centralized version with the aim of reaching the performance upper bound with regards to the accuracy of the model. For doing so, this central node needs to play the role of a central store and allocate the features extracted from the clinical data needed for obtaining this initial version (it is important to mention that the data that need to be available are the features previously extracted from the real health data (particularly for genomics and radiomics data), not the clinical data themselves, so privacy restrictions are considerably lessened. Moreover, in the

case of using additional datasets, the central node will include those which are public or previously pseudonymized).

- ❑ **Step 2: Development and test against an emulated Federated learning platform:**
After obtaining the first non-distributed version of the algorithms, next stage will be to implement them in a distributed way and to test them artificially by assigning different amount of data to different nodes in an asynchronous way, that is, by emulating the federated learning approach. The obtained results are compared with the bound of the previous step to validate the procedure.
- ❑ **Step 3: Federated learning framework deployment and run**
Once the validation is done, a final implementation with real distributed hardware and control software to organize the local and global processing and assigned bandwidth to share the information forth and back between nodes and server needs will allow the final validation and then conclude the procedure.

The evolution of the platform, following these ideas, will be presented in detail in Chapter 5.

3.2 User needs and use case review

Although the gathering of the user needs and the presentation of the principal use cases are the main objectives for WP3, in WP4 the analysis of this information is vital for the definition and design of the complete platform, not only the federated learning part. Bellow it is included a summary with the most important aspects to be considered for each use case according to the user's needs, based on the description given in D3.2 and focused on different hematological diseases such as myelodysplastic syndrome (MS), multiple myeloma (MM) and sickle cell disease (SCD):

- ❑ **Use case 1: Clinical research and care institution joining the platform:**
 - Description and main objective: a clinical center specialized in clinical research and care in one of the project's areas wants to join the platform for providing additional data and for acting as a new node of the federated learning platform that may improve the existing AI algorithms.
 - Main actors: clinical researchers and care providers.
 - Platform functionalities to be provided: according to the description, the platform should allow the following options:
 - To grant access and profiling of the new actors by accounting mechanisms.
 - To allow exploratory queries to the already existing AI models.
 - To allow the subscription to a particular AI model.
 - To allow the inclusion of new edge nodes into the network.
 - To trigger the re-training of the model according to the planning when the requirements about new data are met.
 - To allow the evaluation of the new data contribution to the algorithm, including the validation of the newly data model.

- To allow the notification of a new trained model to the user.
- **Use case 2: Development and testing of new AI models:**
- Description and objective: a clinical care provider contributing to the federated network is able to use the existing models for clinical decision support
 - Main actors: AI developers.
 - Platform functionalities to be provided: according to the description, the platform should allow the following options:
 - To allow the user to register/log in in the system
 - To allow the user to query about existing models
 - To allow the download of synthetic data for the training of new models
 - To allow the launch of the model training
 - To allow the user to check the accuracy of the model
- **Use case 3: Clinical decision support:**
- Description and objective: an AI developer (internal or external) queries for existing AI models in the platform regarding one specific input and decides to develop a new one.
 - Main actors: clinicians.
 - Platform functionalities to be provided: according to the description, the platform should allow the following options:
 - To allow the user to register/log in in the system
 - To allow the user to query the local clinical decision support system (CDSS) that runs the AI model to obtain an answer to specific personalized medicine questions supported by the platform (related to the existing Ai algorithms).
 - To allow the retrieval of the individual case from the hospital to the algorithm in the central node.
 - To allow the predictive result provision

3.3 Additional aspects and constraints

As an innovative research area, federated learning faces different challenges [1] that GenoMed4All hybrid platform should also consider for a proper provision. Following the list fully explained in D6.2, there are two main issues that needs to be addressed from the platform point of view that are listed here and will be further tackled on the following WP4 tasks. On one hand, the selection of a hybrid approach will assure the privacy to the different data owners by never letting raw data out of their premises and just allowing the updates of the models to be sent to the central server, which should be done in a secure way, avoiding any kind of leak. In this way, the platform should assure a secure computation, a privacy preserving disclosure and a way to assess the verifiability of the different parties within the federated learning network. On the other, the communication of local updates and the definition of a compression scheme for reducing the communication load should be also considered.

According to the project's definition, the platform will benefit from the inclusion of a central computing resource HPC centre, which will mainly allow the computing of AI models and training the network. In particular, the rationale behind the need for these high computational capabilities is based on different aspects:

- ❑ As previously said, the first step for the AI federated algorithm provision will be based on a centralized version which will be further distributed. This initial version, focused on the training with the existing data (extracted features from the clinical data), will benefit from this computational power.
- ❑ The partial data aggregation from the local nodes' algorithms after the initial model provision will be managed in the central node.
- ❑ The feature extraction will be executed based on a local strategy for each node, not contemplating the federated feature extraction from the clinical data due to its complexity. Nevertheless, we need to consider this option when designing the platform, since the feature extraction is very computational resources demanding.
- ❑ Finally, for those care centers and hospitals that do not have enough computing power capacity in their premises for executing the different actions such as the feature extraction before the model training, this HPC central server may act as computational capability provider by defining an end-to-end connection for allowing the hospital to manage these tasks.

4 Federated learning platform technical requirements

4.1 Requirements gathering methodology

With the aim of defining the set of requirements that will describe the Genomed4All federated framework functionalities, a specific methodology has been applied. First, a complete analysis of these main functionalities has been made through different tasks along WP3 together with the organization of a specific workshop focused on the platform ideation and provision. After this, the specifications for the individual modules have been derived based on this information and the feedback given by the responsible technical partners.

The general platform engineering methodology is composed of a set of sequential phases that are depicted in the following figure, that reflect part of the system analysis of the project which is complemented by the definition of the user needs (from D3.2) that leads to the requirements acquisition and platform specification. Then, the definition of the platform architecture, together with a detailed design, comes afterwards. Finally, the implementation, integration and validation of the federated infrastructure will complete the full workflow. Moreover, the results coming from the validation would be used as important feedback for improving the platform and assuring the accomplishment of the project's objectives related to the federated approach.

Fig. 3. GenoMed4All platform engineering methodology

It is evident that the Requirement Acquisition and Platform Specification tasks are vital to the effective development of a project such as GenoMed4All, which is composed of a different number of modules and offer distinct functionalities. Due to this complexity, it is expected that the requirements definition will not be covered by a sequential approach and therefore more requirement analysis iterations will be required through the development of the infrastructure. In this sense, some requirements may be modified after the specification phase, while others may appear along the implementation and integration process.

The platform's design lifecycle is shown in Fig. 4, where the most important information depicted is the association of the project phases with the platform monitoring and validation that will take place in T4.4. This monitoring uses a new kind of element called validation indicators, which will be defined as the same point as the requirements to help with the quantification of the validation.

Fig. 4. GenoMed4All platform lifecycle that includes how to obtain, define, implement and verify the functional (FR) and non-functional (NFR) requirements

4.2 Requirement definition issues

While performing the platform requirements elicitation procedure some issues came across due to the fact that each work package and even each partner have not always the same idea about the feasibility of the system, the modules to be included and the boundaries between the different work package responsibilities, especially among the technical ones. Therefore, the requirement acquisition and system specification tasks developed within WP3 (user requirements and use case definition), WP4 (federated learning platform requirements) and WP5 (data engineering requirements) can be considered as the first approach to develop a common understanding of the system functionalities.

Although requirements elicitation is a relatively mature area in requirement engineering and the partners in the consortium have plenty of experience within this kind of tasks, it is always important to have in mind that a correct, complete, and coherent provision is vital for a proper design and implementation. For this reason, during this stage a special effort was conducted in order to avoid the main problems that usually appear while producing the final definitions according to [1].

Table 1. Most common issues regarding requirement elicitation and related solutions within GenoMed4All context

	Description	Solution
Noise	Information that does not carry relevant data to any feature	The application of use cases and scenarios as the development methodology system for the project helped in the detection of this issue
Silence	A feature that is not covered by any element	The application of use cases and scenarios as the development methodology system for the project helped in the detection of this issue
Over-specification	An element that corresponds not to a feature of the problem but to features of a possible solution	Dynamic examination of the rationale regarding each requirement
Contradiction	Two or more elements that define a feature of the system in an incompatible way	Dynamic examination of the rationale regarding each requirement
Ambiguity	An element that makes it possible to interpret a feature of the problem in at least two different ways	Dynamic examination of the rationale regarding each requirement
Forward reference	An element that uses features of the problem not defined until later	Dynamic examination of the rationale regarding each requirement
Wishful thinking	An element that defines a feature on the problem in such a way that a candidate solution cannot realistically be validated with respect to this feature	The application of use cases and scenarios as the development methodology system for the project helped in the detection of this issue

As can be seen in Table 1, the importance of the use cases is clearly reflected in the requirement definition process. In this regard, the following section describes in more detail how the use cases generated in D3.2 and summarized in Section 3.2 have been applied as input in this task.

4.3 Requirement negotiation

Considering the description of the project, we can define two main types of stakeholders for the GenoMed4All federated learning platform: the clinical partners and the AI researchers, both providing valuable inputs in the requirements gathering procedure. Therefore, the design and development efforts will try to satisfy their user needs that have been analytically documented in D3.2

Nevertheless, the challenge of producing innovative ideas for the system provision can be seen as a task for the entire consortium, where all partners should be asked for their own contributions with the aim of increasing the impact of the project. For this reason, the description of the use cases and scenarios included in the proposal must be complemented and improved with additional information coming from different actions that allow the contribution exchange in a creative way. For doing so, a specific workshop focused on the ideation of the platform was planned just some months after the beginning of the project and prior to the start of WP4 with the idea of having some information derived from the first work period but with some time to work on it to obtain important data for the requirements definition. The workshop was divided into three different sessions to not overwhelm the attendees and to try to boost their contributions from the first to the second and third meetings. Moreover, during each session the attendees were divided into different multidisciplinary groups to allow specific breakout sessions that helped the interaction and discussion, having in all of them the opportunity to collect notes and produce draft requirements. The specific dates when these two sessions took place and the main issues discussed in each one are presented in the following table:

Table 2. Platform ideation workshops' information

Session	Date	Issues to discuss
First session: Central store capabilities	17/06/2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding federated learning Platform evolution: central to federated Related questions to be discussed during the breakout sessions
Second session: Federated learning use cases and capabilities (I)	09/07/2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Macro use case: research Macro use case: Clinician decision support.
Third session: Federated learning use case and capabilities (II)	15/07/2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The federated learning use cases Related questions to be discussed during the breakout sessions

As planned, the information obtained from these sessions helped not only WP3 in the definition of the users' requirements but also WP4 in the identification of the first draft of the federated platform requirements. Finally, it is important to note that, after these workshops and during the requirements gathering, the details of some specific requirements have been consulted to the related stakeholders, especially those related to the AI models' provision (WP6) The following table shows the questions sent to the AI experts and the related answers obtained from UPM, UNITO and UCPH in an aggregated way:

Table 3. information coming from WP6 for the requirements definition

Question	Comment	Answer
What kind of data is your model going to exchange between nodes?	Prior to training stage, what kind of data will flow through the network? Possible answers: numerical values, files, strings, etc.	This is not specific of AI and depends on the selected platform, identification of nodes, ACKs...
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For defining the training phases 	How do you define the training plan on client nodes? Said differently which parameters do you consider important to consider into a training plan (for ex frequency of training, specificity/sensitivity/xx threshold, default behaviour in case of error during training etc ...)	Iterative process with asynchronous local updates, sharing information, global processing at the central server and feedback to the nodes. Monitoring the training process to verify right convergence (threshold). The training will take place at the network creation and updated not very often (months)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For the model obtaining 	During the federated training which kind of data needs the model to be exchanged? Only numerical data? Same as 1 but during training. For example, should we consider long run training phase that may need to be monitored (execution error, or other key monitoring parameters to consider)	Numerical (real) values representing the model parameters or samples of distributions
Which library (pytorch, tensorflow, numpy, scikitlearn, etc.) are you going to use?		All of these and other standard Python libraries
Which aggregation strategy is going to be followed by your model?	The aggregation process must be "protected" by the framework (in term of security) such as no non-identified actor may produce a model aggregation on behalf of somebody else. So which aggregation method do you expect the framework to support (AVG etc ...)	The aggregation will be very algorithmic specific and should be defined by the AI algorithm as part of the training process.

Do you expect to receive any information about the data quality assessment?		Yes
Security the model broadcast to the edge	Do you see any constraint for encrypting & decrypting the model that you will create (For security reasons to be sure that no Man in the middle push other models to the edge)	No, encryption can be implemented on top
Edge node registration	If we consider an edge registration process into the framework, which AI parameters are important from your perspective to accept or not a node. For example, supported library, processing capacity, storage capacity etc.	Yes, this has to be implemented off-line
Checking model deployment	Once a model is deployed on an edge node, what are the parameters to check that it is operational for training? Do you plan to introduce some "check-up" process in your model to validate that everything is ok for starting the training?	Yes, this has to be implemented off-line
Training control	Do you think that a set of training "control" commands (from the central node to an edge) is necessary? For example, "pause", "resume", "check status" etc.	Yes

4.4 Major platform requirements

Once the general methodology for requirements elicitation has been presented, as well as the main related issues and negotiation, the next step is to provide an extensive list of the identified requirements. At this point it is important to remember that, according to the main scope of this deliverable, the set of requirements to be listed are related to the federated learning platform approach, not the entire GenoMed4All system. In this regard, this initial list should be increased and improved by other tasks focused on other aspects of the platform, such as the general functionalities for the central computing resource HPC centre (T4.3) and the data engineering modules (WP5). Moreover, the identification of these requirements has helped in the analysis of the federated learning framework solution to be chosen, as it will be lately explained in Chapter 6.

With the aim of providing a complete view of this analysis, each requirement will be presented with a specific table containing all the related information: identifier, type, related component of the federated learning infrastructure, function name, capability details, priority (according to the MoSCoW method [2]), validation, related use case and last update.

As can be seen, the requirements are related to the main two components of the architecture: the central server (“server”) and the nodes (“edge”), and they can be divided into different types or categories according to the phase of the federated learning process they affect (building and deployment of the model, execution and monitor, listing and display, etc.)

Table 4. REQ-B&D-1 description

Requirement No	1
Requirement ID	REQ-B&D-1
Type	Functional, Build and deploy
Related component	Server
Function name	Building a training plan definition (by packaging the components and easily deploying them to a set of nodes)
Capability details	The training plan will include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The initial model with the associated parameters - The training data cohort definition. - The training workflow
Integration into the platform	The training plan is defined by means of a config file that can be easily saved/restored
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 5. REQ-B&D-2 description

Requirement No	2
Requirement ID	REQ-B&D-2
Type	Functional, Build and deploy
Related component	Server
Function name	List/display edge node system resources
Capability details	The info to be provided: CPU, memory, storage capabilities, etc.
Integration into the platform	The communication protocol allows reporting to the server the current edges system resources to be aggregated by the server through a central fed learning management console
Priority	Should have
Validation	Yes/no

Last update	15/12/2021
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Table 6. REQ-B&D-3 description

Requirement No	3
Requirement ID	REQ-B&D-3
Type	Functional, Build and deploy
Related component	Server
Function name	List/display edge node dataset metadata
Capability details	The metadata should describe the clinical/-omics features and the availability/status/readiness and quality metrics
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Should have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 7. REQ-B&D-4 description

Requirement No	4
Requirement ID	REQ-B&D-4
Type	Functional, Build and deploy
Related component	Server
Function name	Preparing the deployment
Capability details	Access to the edge data set quality metric for checking real system performance
Integration into the platform	The communication protocol allows reporting to the server the dataset quality based on metrics provided by the framework
Priority	Should have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 8. REQ-B&D-5 description

Requirement No	5
Requirement ID	REQ-B&D-5

Type	Functional, Build and deploy
Related component	Server
Function name	Deploying a training plan to the edge
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The communication protocol allows deploying the training plan and provides report status to the central server management console
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 9. REQ-E&M-6 description

Requirement No	6
Requirement ID	REQ-E&M-6
Type	Functional, Execute and monitor
Related component	Server
Function name	Remote control of edge training plan execution
Capability details	Allowing start/stop/resume/cancel options
Integration into the platform	Any error should be reported. This function should be consolidated into the management console
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 10. REQ-E&M-7 description

Requirement No	7
Requirement ID	REQ-E&M-7
Type	Functional, Execute and monitor
Related component	Server
Function name	Tracking training plan execution

Capability details	Tracking training step errors and progress per node per model
Integration into the platform	The communication protocol allows reporting training plan execution error and status. This function should be consolidated into the management console
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 11. REQ-E&M-8 description

Requirement No	8
Requirement ID	REQ-E&M-8
Type	Functional, Execute and monitor
Related component	Server
Function name	Saving training plan definition
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The saving procedure produces a content that can be archived on a file system for later retrieval and usage
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 12. REQ-E&M-9 description

Requirement No	9
Requirement ID	REQ-E&M-9
Type	Functional, Execute and monitor
Related component	Server
Function name	Sending an aggregated model to the edge
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The communication protocol allows reporting operation status. This function should be consolidated into the management console
Priority	Must have

Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 13. REQ-R-10 description

Requirement No	10
Requirement ID	REQ-R-10
Type	Functional, Remove
Related component	Server
Function name	Removing a training plan
Capability details	By cascading the remove of the training plan into the edge
Integration into the platform	The communication protocol allows reporting operation status. This function should be consolidated into the management console
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 14. REQ-E&M-11 description

Requirement No	11
Requirement ID	REQ-E&M-11
Type	Functional, Execute and monitor
Related component	Edge
Function name	Star/stop/resume/delete a training plan
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 15. REQ-L&D-12 description

Requirement No	12
Requirement ID	REQ-L&D-12

Type	Functional, List and display
Related component	Edge
Function name	List/display available training plan deployed from the server
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 16. REQ-L&D-13 description

Requirement No	13
Requirement ID	REQ-L&D-13
Type	Functional, List and display
Related component	Edge
Function name	List/display referenced system resource
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 17. REQ-L&D-14 description

Requirement No	14
Requirement ID	REQ-L&D-14
Type	Functional, List and display
Related component	Edge
Function name	List/display edge node dataset metadata
Capability details	The metadata should describe the clinical/genomics features and the availability/status/readiness and quality metrics

Integration into the platform	
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 18. REQ-L&D-15 description

Requirement No	15
Requirement ID	REQ-L&D-15
Type	Functional, List and display
Related component	Edge
Function name	List/display/discovery dataset content
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 19. REQ-CD-16 description

Requirement No	16
Requirement ID	REQ-CD-16
Type	Functional, Control Dataset
Related component	Edge
Function name	Adding a new dataset
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 20. REQ-CD-17 description

Requirement No	17
Requirement ID	REQ-CD-17
Type	Functional, Control Dataset
Related component	Edge
Function name	Removing an existing dataset
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 21. REQ-GI-18 description

Requirement No	18
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-18
Type	General Integration,
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework component deployment and uninstall
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	Each component is available in a docker form factor to be integrated into the main platform deployment scenario
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 22. REQ-GI-19 description

Requirement No	19
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-19
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge

Function name	Framework component control with a CLI
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	Each software component of the framework is instrumented with a CLI
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 23. REQ-GI-20 description

Requirement No	20
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-20
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework component control via API
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	Each software component of the framework can be configured and controlled via API
Priority	Should have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 24. REQ-GI-21 description

Requirement No	21
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-21
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework component configuration
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	Each component installation and configuration (with mandatory and optional parameters) is accessible as a config file from a container orchestrator

Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 25. REQ-GI-22 description

Requirement No	22
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-22
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Backup and restore
Capability details	Models, training plan, dataset, etc. can be backup and restored in case of failure
Integration into the platform	The backup procedure produces a content that can be archived on a file system
Priority	Should have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 26. REQ-GI-23 description

Requirement No	23
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-23
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework component log
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	Each software component of the framework is equipped with a proper logging service
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 27. REQ-GI-24 description

Requirement No	24
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Requirement ID	REQ-GI-24
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework component audit
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	
Priority	Should have
Validation	Yes/No
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 28. REQ-GI-25 description

Requirement No	25
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-25
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework component security
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	Component operation is under authentication control and the execution of each script and process are properly configured to respect the file system access control mechanism
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 29. REQ-GI-26 description

Requirement No	26
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-26
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework AI/ML libraries support

Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The framework is able to support different AI libraries, especially python libraries
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 30. REQ-GI-27 description

Requirement No	27
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-27
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework AI/ML differential privacy
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The framework is able to include differential privacy for personal data protection
Priority	Should have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 31. REQ-GI-28 description

Requirement No	28
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-28
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server and edge
Function name	Framework AI/ML model agnostic
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The framework is able to operate with different AI models
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no

Last update	15/12/2021
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Table 32. REQ-GI-29 description

Requirement No	29
Requirement ID	REQ-GI-29
Type	General Integration
Related component	Server
Function name	Framework AI/ML aggregation strategy
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The framework is able to allow different aggregation strategies
Priority	Must have
Validation	Short answer
Last update	15/12/2021

Table 33. REQ-E&M-30 description

Requirement No	30
Requirement ID	REQ-E&M-30
Type	Functional, Execute and monitor
Related component	Server
Function name	Saving a model (part of a training plan)
Capability details	
Integration into the platform	The system has to allow the model to be saved
Priority	Must have
Validation	Yes/no
Last update	15/12/2021

Apart from these functional requirements, there are additional aspect to be considered, especially for identifying the best federated learning framework to be selected for the project:

- Interoperability: the system shall use (open, when available) standards to exchange information between different nodes (Must have).

- ❑ Usability: specific documentation for installing, updating and running the software should be provided.
 - The system should be usable for the different final users (Must have)
 - Specific documentation for installing, updating and running the software should be provided (Must have).
- ❑ Project sustainability: the federated learning framework to be used must be open source.
- ❑ Federated learning framework setup aspects about the solution to be chosen:
 - Easy to customize
 - Interoperability with external tools
 - Complexity
 - Documentation available
 - Support
 - Examples available
 - Project lifecycle and governance
 - Project's partners background expertise
 - Reference deployments
 - Community size

5 Design of the GenoMed4All federated learning platform

5.1 Platform actors and components

As has been previously said, D3.2 identified 3 macro use cases. The detailed analysis of these ones ended up with 2 operating models:

- ❑ A first one, focused on research, aims at producing AI models for serving the care practices for patients affected by rare hematological diseases. It refers to use case 1 and 2.
- ❑ A second one focused on the decision support process used by clinicians during the care workflow. It refers to use case 3.

5.1.1 Research

For this operating model a set of 5 macro steps have been identified, as shown in Fig. 5:

Fig. 5. Research operation model workflow description

The main macro functions and associated actors for each step are presented below:

- ❑ **Step-1: Organization research**
 - **Functions:** Org profile registration (training capabilities, data sets, agreement)
Anonymized sample dataset integration to CDM
 - **Actors:** Clinical Care provider, Clinical researcher, and data scientists
- ❑ **Step-2: Initial model def & training**
 - **Functions:**
 - Data exploration
 - Building training plan
 - Define model validation criteria
 - Define data cohort specs
 - Train initial model
 - Select edge & send model + data-cohort specs
 - **Actors**
 - Clinical research and data scientists
- ❑ **Step-3: Model pre/run/mon @edge**
 - **Functions**

- builds the data-set using the training plan & data-cohort specs
- Deploy/Apply/Monitor training plan
- Sends the trained model back to the central along with the training report
- **Actors**
 - Clinical care providers

□ Step-4: Model evaluation & aggregation

- **Functions:**
 - Received trained model & reports through the model mngr.
 - Applies aggregation method (AVG etc.)
 - Validates the new trained model (no shift, accuracy)
 - Register new model version for next training round
- **Actors**
 - Clinical research and data scientists

□ Step-5: Model management

- **Functions:**
 - Central Sends new model version & new training plan to edge
 - Edge deploy the model version to CDS & apply new training plan
 - Edge monitor training
- **Actors**
 - Clinical research and data scientists
 - Org IT Data specialist

5.1.2 Care delivery

For this operating model a set of 2 macro phases have been identified, as shown in Fig. 6:

Fig. 6. Care delivery operation model workflow description

In this above process, 2 macro phases have been identified. The first one is closely related to the Research operating model presented above. The last step is the deployment of the model to the CDS. This deployment takes place recurrently based on the different FL rounds. The second one is dealing with care activities. The different steps are presented below with functions and actors.

□ Step-1: Genomic test ordering

- **Functions**
 - Indication for genetic test

- Submit test order
 - Specimen collection
 - **Actors**
 - Clinician
- ❑ **Step-2: Specimen proc & tests**
- **Functions**
 - Receive order, specimen
 - Processing, testing
 - Bioinformatics analysis
 - **Actors**
 - Laboratory / Bio-info specialist
- ❑ **Step-3: Transcoding / Interpretation**
- **Functions**
 - Transcoding
 - Interpretation
 - **Actors**
 - Genetics Molecular pathologist
- ❑ **Step-4: HC Analysis (using CDS)**
- **Functions**
 - Interpret Genomic-report
 - Collect patient data & Submit CDS query
 - Finalise diagnostic & care plan
 - **Actors**
 - Clinician

5.2 Platform actors and components

Fig. 7 presents the high-level architecture of the Genomed4All platform, that is composed of the following modules:

- ❑ A central component whose objectives are the following:
 - Hosting the Common data model and the pseudonymized dataset provided by the care providers contributing to the development and federated training of model. These data sets have been pseudonymized by care providers before being uploaded into the central store and they are composed of the features extracted from the original datasets, in order to assure the information privacy. These datasets are used to develop the first version of the model and test it. Not all care providers contributing to model development have necessary expertise to provide pseudonymized data. What is key is that the dataset is 1) sufficiently exhaustive to expose all the features required by Data scientist 2) sufficiently representative of the different care provider data sets (that will be used at the edge for

training the model) such that, when the model is deployed to the edge, missing features do not hinder the central model overall training process.

- Hosting the common Data model & the dataset provided by care providers when they do not have the capabilities to train a model at the edge. This situation is similar to a classical central model training mode. It justifies the term hybrid for the GenoMed4All platform.
- Running the FL server functions. We distinguish:
 - The capabilities in charge of handling the full model life-cycle, defining the training plan, browsing edge meta-data datasets, creating the data cohort and selecting/monitoring the edge contributors (model management), aggregating the inputs models (from the edge).
 - The capabilities in charge of securing the framework. This includes encrypting/decrypting the model, maintaining a secured communication path with edges.
 - The capabilities to onboard new edge components. This includes registering their training capabilities, available dataset (as meta-data), framework connection points.
 - The capabilities to train a model (worker). This function is referring the hybrid working mode of the platform when a care provider does not have the capabilities to train a model at the edge and so accept to run in a classical centralized training model.
 - An edge component whose objectives are the following:
 - Running the Federated learning edge functions. We distinguish
 - The capabilities in charge of securing the framework. This includes encrypting/decrypting the model, maintaining a secured communication path with central.
 - The capabilities to train a model. This function is similar to the worker element in the central server.
 - The Clinical Decision Support (CDS) is referring to the function accessed by the clinical from the EHR.

Fig. 7. GenoMed4All high level infrastructure

A FL model life cycle has been defined leveraging the approached proposed by [3]. Fig. 8 presents this model which distinguishes the Central and Edge location the model state refers to.

Fig. 8. General model lifecycle that includes where the main activities are implemented (central server or edge)

Based on this state model, a more granular analysis has been conducted to identify, for each state (or group of):

- ❑ the use-case underlying the execution of the state
- ❑ the macro objects that this state will handle
- ❑ the framework messages (or macro messages) which either trigger or output the state
- ❑ the software function executing the state

This preliminary works is presented below. It is a first high level proposal that will be used as a reference to T4.2 for:

- ❑ Defining the high and low level specifications of the FL framework
- ❑ Building a delivery plan which will ends up with:
 - Selected functions to implement (based on priorities and resources)
 - An agenda for the delivery plan

The Edge registration takes place each time a new actor wants to enter the FL network:

Fig. 9. Edge registration

The following figures present the different state (or group of) of the different phases of the model life cycle for GEnoMed4All:

Fig. 10. Model definition and initial phase

Model preparation @central

Scenario

- The Data scientist selects a set of destinating edge clients
- The data scientist packages the training plan along with the *initial model*
- The Fwk Central send it to the edge client(s)
- He receives an acknowledgment that the training plan has been deployed and that the model training has started.

Objects

- Edge profile
- Training plan

Function (central)

- Client Manager
 - broadcast model

Fig. 11. Model preparation at the central part

Model preparation @edge

Scenario

- The Fwk edge *builds* the data-set from the local repository using the training plan details
- The Fwk edge applies the training plan (model accuracy, nb of retraining etc ...)
- The Fwk edge *monitors* the training plan and stops it when needed
- The Fwk edge sends the trained model back to the central along with the training report

Objects involved

- Training plan
- Training report

Function (edge)

- Edge orchestrator
 - Build data plan
 - run model
 - Monitor model

Fig. 12. Model preparation at the edge

Model evaluation

Scenario

- The Data scientist received the trained model through the model mngr.
- Using its own data science tools he applies aggregation method (AVG etc ..)
- Using its own data science tools he validates that this new trained model can be added to the central model (no shift, accuracy) using the Model validation criteria

Objects involved

- Training report
- Model validation criteria

Function (central)

- Model manager
- Data science tools

Fig. 13. Model evaluation

Model deployment

Scenario

- The Data scientist deploys the model to the edge along with a updated training plan
- The Fwk edge installs the model into the Clinical decision support

Function (central)

- Client Selector
 - deploy model
- Edge orchestrator
 - Install model (to CDS)

Fig. 14. Model deployment

Scenario

- The edge node *monitors* the model training & send a new version upon reaching the model validation criteria

Function (edge)

- Edge orchestrator
 - Update data plan
 - run model
 - Monitor model

Objects involved

- Training plan

Fig. 15. Model monitoring

5.3 Data provision

The final platform to be provided will include three main parts:

- ❑ The FL platform
- ❑ The common data model (CDM) used both by the edge and central function.
- ❑ The AI/ML algorithms to be training on the platform.

Moreover, the modules to be included in the platform are presented in Fig. 16, where each of them will be implemented within the different technical work packages of the project. In particular:

- ❑ The general platform will be responsible for integrating the various components such that it can run in production and integrate new diseases / algorithm / care providers actors in the ecosystem. This requires enforcing a number of robust integration functions during the development phase of the FL framework as well as other collateral functions (logging, security, high availability, etc.).
- ❑ With regards to the federated learning framework, two sets of components will be deployed as it was previously mentioned: one in the central server and one in the different edge nodes.
- ❑ Finally, a core task will be the development and testing of the initial model that will feed the FL process. This task requires data in a format that exposes the required capabilities. A CDM has been chosen with FHIR, but, since it exposes features that are not directly applicable to AI/ML algorithm, some data preparation (data normalization, alignment, extraction of advanced features) is required. This preparation is going to be handled by a data transformation pipeline (so called last mile pipeline technology) provided by the platform. A specific data pipe will refer to each algorithm. This pipeline definition will then be referenced by the training plan object. This object will be deployed at the edge and a similar last mile data pipeline will be executed by the edge federated learning component to extract the data from the CDM and expose them to the Data-API (used by the algorithm to train the model).

Fig. 16. Platform modules according to the different work packages

6 GenoMed4All federated learning platform implementation guidelines

6.1 Federated learning solutions state of the art

Federated learning is a rapidly evolving subject and many FL frameworks projects have been started in the last 3-4 years, according to a relevant paper in the field [5]. There were 6 frameworks considered as production oriented and moreover we also evaluated 3 more relevant frameworks (TensorFlow Federated, FedBiomed and PySyft/PyGrid):

- FATE²
- PaddleFL³
- Clara training Framework⁴
- IBM Federated Learning⁵
- Flower Framework⁶
- FedLearner⁷
- FedBiomed⁸
- TensorFlow Federated⁹
- PySyft/PyGrid¹⁰

6.2 Evaluation criteria

The requirements analysis for the frameworks has been in-depth, even breaking down the items below. However, we note that the final selection criterion can be compressed into a set of criteria described below:

- Building and deployment of training plan. Training phases definition (initial model parameters, data definition, training workflow); data to be exchanged; list system resources
- Execution and monitorization of training plan. Data quality assessment; checkup process before execution; tracking training progress.
- Authentication / security
- AI libraries. Framework offers viability to use different AI libraries, depending on scientist needs.

² <https://fate.fedai.org/>

³ <https://github.com/PaddlePaddle/PaddleFL>

⁴ <https://docs.nvidia.com/clara/clara-train-sdk/pt/index.html>

⁵ <https://ibmfl.mybluemix.net/>

⁶ <https://flower.dev/>

⁷ <https://github.com/bytedance/fedlearner>

⁸ <https://gitlab.inria.fr/fedbiomed>

⁹ <https://www.tensorflow.org/federated?hl=es>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft/>

- This was a strong requirement brought forward by the WP6, which was that the FL framework should be able to support any python based AI/ML library (pytorch, tensorflow, etc.), based on this requirement we had to filter out many FL frameworks (most of them were either pytorch or tensorflow friendly).
- ❑ Aggregation strategy. Combination of weights information from different edges to central node, including ability to personalize the strategy apart from default one.
- ❑ Easy to customize. Possibility of including new functionalities on top of the platform and according to needs.
- ❑ Documentation and examples. Set of available information to help developers and scientists to install, execute and control framework.
- ❑ Background expertise. Previous experience between project partners of the Genomed4All project.
- ❑ Open source. The selected FL framework should have a source code license which allow to modify and contribute to the code and which is also commercial friendly for a possible exploitation once the project is over. Apache 2 and MIT for examples are two types of licenses which comply with the GenoMed4All requirements
- ❑ Legal assessment and IPR management. The selected solution should not get into conflict with the IPR management strategies defined by the consortium.

Among all the FL frameworks described in the 6.1 section, we chose to evaluate only 3 FL frameworks, Flower, Fedbiomed and FATE. This is due to the fact that the GenoMed4all AI work package (WP6) stated that the FL framework has to be compatible with all the python AI framework, therefore we could drop many frameworks from the initial list.

6.3 FL framework main solutions analysis

As mentioned above, the evaluated frameworks are FATE, Flower and Fedbiomed. The following sub sections are going to present each of them.

6.3.1 FATE

FATE is an open-source project initiated by Webank's AI Department to provide a secure computing framework to support the federated AI ecosystem. It implements multiple secure computation protocols to enable big data collaboration with data protection regulation compliance.

Fig. 17. FATE architecture (from <https://fate.fedai.org/>)

6.3.2 FLOWER FRAMEWORK

Flower is an open-source simple scalable model agnostic FL framework that handles communications via RPC (Remote Procedure Call) protocol. RPC has a nice interaction with docker containers as it doesn't need to publish the ports of the worker (client) nodes. Flower is simple to use and supports numerous frameworks or even custom python code, hence it is also pythonic and thus delivers an easy-to-use API.

One of the most important requirements for the sandbox is that the FL service is not intended for the technical team, but for the SMEs. That is why it is not enough to produce model agnostic API, but also a clean and easy to use interface. This way, even if the SMEs are not proficient in producing a FL model, the complexity is hidden in the background and the model python scripts are straightforward.

Flower needs two different scripts with completely different roles: a central server where individual models are combined and a client training on the node data at each iteration, and implementation of the server code combining models and client code regarding each of the training steps. Moreover, Flower just introduces approximately 20 lines of code adding up both client and server codes, in its basic usage example. Fig. 18 shows the main architecture of this framework.

Fig. 18. FLOWER core framework architecture (from <https://flower.dev/docs/architecture.html>)

6.3.3 FEDBIOMED

Fed-BioMed is an open-source project focused on empowering biomedical research using non-centralized approaches for statistical analysis and machine learning. The project is currently based on Python, PyTorch and Scikit-learn, and enables developing and deploying federated learning analysis in real-world machine learning applications.

Fig. 19. Common FL scenario for FedBiomed (from <https://gitlab.inria.fr/fedbiomed>)

The goal of Fed-BioMed is to provide a simplified and secured environment to:

- ❑ Easily deploy state-of-the-art federated learning analysis frameworks.
- ❑ Provide a friendly user interface to share data for federated learning experiments.
- ❑ Allow researchers to easily deploy their models and analysis methods.
- ❑ Foster research and collaborations in federated learning.

6.4 Assessment of candidate solutions

Table 34 shows additional information per framework about criteria selection.

Table 34. Summary of the candidates' analysis according to the criteria listed above

N°	Criteria	FATE	Flower	FedBiomed
1	Building and deployment of training plan	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Execution and monitorization of training plan	DSL, and log	Python class and log	DSL and log
3	Authentication / security	-	SSL	VPN

4	AI libraries	PyTorch, TensorFlow and some ScikitLearn	All python based library	Pytorch, some ScikitLearn model.
5	Aggregation strategy	Yes, customizable	Yes, customizable	Yes, customizable
6	Easy to customize	Medium	High with extension	Medium
7	Documentation and examples	Medium	Medium	Low
8	Background expertise	No	UPM, UNIBO	No
9	Open source	Yes	Yes	Yes
10	Legal assessment & IPR management	Aligned with GenoMed4all	Aligned with GenoMed4all	Potential issue with ownership transfer

6.4.1 Assessment analysis

6.4.1.1 Building and deployment of training plan

Fate: The first step is to define a parameter object, register the metadata information of the new component and then define the transfer variable object. All the details on how to perform those steps are explained in [6].

Flower: The training plan has to be downloaded from a central place to the nodes.

FedBiomed: The training plan is defined together with the model, and it is stored in a django framework, the nodes download it from the server once they start the FL process.

6.4.1.2 Execution and monitorization of training plan

Fate: The execution is done by submitting a job via the Fate Domain Specific Language (DSL) and the monitoring is done by checking the log files.

Flower: The execution is done by calling the python flower class and all the relevant information of the training process are printed in the log.

FedBiomed: The execution is done by using the Fedbiomed DSL and all the relevant information are printed in the log.

6.4.1.3 Authentication / security

Fate: It is not clear from the documentation how security is implemented.

Flower: The GRPC communication between the nodes and the server can be done via SSL [7], it needs further work to implement also a token-based authentication level.

FedBiomed: Security is meant to be provided by setting up a VPN among the nodes.

6.4.1.4 AI libraries

Fate: Python based. In latest releases it is starting to support some features from Pytorch, tensorflow and ScikitLearn.

Flower: Python based. General libraries: TensorFlow, PyTorch, scikit, sklearn, numpy based model, very flexible.

FedBiomed: Only Pytorch by now and some scikit learn models

6.4.1.5 Aggregation strategy

Fate: the aggregator class can be extended [8].

Flower: The Flower server does not prescribe a way to persist model updates or evaluation results. Flower does not (yet) automatically save model updates on the server-side. It's on the roadmap to provide a built-in way of doing this. Model updates can be persisted on the server-side by customizing Strategy methods. Implementing custom strategies is always an option, but for many cases it may be more convenient to simply customize an existing strategy.

FedBiomed: In FedBioMed, they currently work on providing various solutions for this heterogeneity. Up to now, they support a function called FedAverage() which performs the standard aggregation scheme in federated learning: federated averaging. It performs a weighted mean of local model parameters based on the size of node specific datasets. This operation occurs after each round of training in the nodes. It is possible to create your custom aggregator by creating a new class which inherits from the Aggregator class.

6.4.1.6 Easy to customize

Fate: It is a quite complex framework and it covers many aspects of a FL framework.

Flower: Flower is a “minimalist” framework which offers the core functionalities of FL framework but it is not “full-battery” framework, neither a ready to use platform. This philosophy/approach

allows an easy customization and integration with other tools/modules. It can be easily built on top. UPM has experience to develop tools on this framework.

FedBiomed: Some modules in FedBiommed can be easily extended/customised, such as the data loader, some other module such as the model distribution to the nodes are more difficult to be customized.

6.4.1.7 Documentation and examples

Fate: Medium size documentation. However, in the initial tests to install the framework it could not be installed due to unexplained problems. Part of the documentation is not translated to English.

Flower: Medium size documentation. Includes various examples.

FedBiomed: Short documentation with the basic steps to run the framework.

6.4.1.8 Background expertise

Fate: None.

Flower: UPM and UNIBO

FedBiomed: None

6.4.1.9 Open source

Fate: Apache 2.0¹¹.

Flower: Apache 2.0¹².

FedBiomed: Apache 2.0 modified, under signing agreements and development will be owned by FedBiomed consortium¹³.

6.4.1.10 Legal assessment and IPR management

Fate: the procedures are described in [9] and [10].

Flower: you can contribute to the source code and keep the ownership of the contribution [11].

¹¹ <https://github.com/FederatedAI/FATE/blob/master/LICENSE>

¹² <https://github.com/adap/flower/blob/main/LICENSE>

¹³ <https://gitlab.inria.fr/fedbiomed/fedbiomed/-/blob/master/LICENSE.md>

FedBiomed: Right now, they have developed project specific requirements. Any contribution will be placed under Apache 2.0 license and transfers the IP rights to Inria/UCA.

6.4.2 Evaluation and reasoning

FedBiomed is a very promising and complete FL framework that covers many of the needs of a FL framework, the weak points for us are the IPR management, because all the contributions to the framework should transfer the IPR ownership to INRIA and also the fact that at the moment only pytorch is fully supported, another source of risk was the use of MQTT protocol for communication which is optimal for short message communication but not for large message communication.

FATE is a very complete FL framework and is managed under the Linux foundation, there are many modules and features and not always the documentation covers well all the aspects hence the extension and customization of the FL framework for the GenoMed4All purposes can be a challenge. Moreover, it is not clear if FATE can support all the AI python libraries and how much efforts should be done to add new libraries. At the moment it is very focused to TensorFlow and PyTorch. Anyway, it is a FL framework which can be used as reference implementation for many aspects and it could be considered a second option in the case Flower will not perform as expected. Additionally, in the preliminary tests performed by the Genomed4All consortium, the installation and execution of initial examples raised some issues that the consortium couldn't solve by following the documentation of the solution.

Flower is a minimalist FL framework built on solid foundations such as gRPC and protobuf, it is also very flexible regarding the python AI libraries and the aggregation strategies, it will need to be integrated with other already existing modules and with modules written in Genomed4All in order to cover all the needs that the GenoMed4all will require but we believe that it also the easiest FL framework to be customized or extended.

Given that the requirements defined are generic, a solution that is more mature could raise some issues for adapting it for the Genomed4All project needs. For this reason, among the other aspects previously exposed, the selected solution is Flower.

6.5 Additional needed modules not included in the FL framework selected

Flower is a low-level FL framework, so it means that it does provide a solid core functionality such as Federated training and communication based on GPRC and protobuf, this flexibility offers us to address the two main requirements we captured from WP6, which are plugging any aggregation strategy and support any python-based ML model.

After checking the modules provided by Flower, there are some other functionalities that are needed and should be implemented on top of the framework. A first approach of these functionalities is:

- ❑ Http(s) communication, needed for UI and common API interaction, a possible solution will be to embed/run flower into a flask server or some async python server.
- ❑ Security seen as authentication and authorization (OpenID token could be used for authentication and GRPC supports it, while authorization should be harmonized with datasets permission.
- ❑ Model management, MLflow could be evaluated as an option.
- ❑ Data uploader, it should provide a CSV uploader, but we can also evaluate more sophisticated uploader (from FHIR, phenopackets, git, etc.).
- ❑ User management or identity provider, Keycloak could be evaluated.

For the provision of these services, and referring to the platform requirements defined in section 4.4, Table 34 presents the current status of Flower framework with respect to platform requirements:

Table 35. Functionalities to be provided and related Flower status

Req. ID	Req. description	Provided by Flower?
REQ-B&D-1	Building a training plan definition (by packaging the components and easily deploying them to a set of nodes)	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-B&D-2	List/display edge node system resources	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-B&D-3	List/display edge node dataset metadata	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-B&D-4	Preparing the deployment	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-B&D-5	Deploying a training plan to the edge	Implemented
REQ-E&M-6	Remote control of edge training plan execution	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-E&M-7	Tracking training plan execution	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-E&M-8	Saving training plan definition	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-E&M-9	Sending an aggregated model to the edge	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-R-10	Removing a training plan	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-E&M-11	Star/stop/resume/delete a training plan	Not directly. To be implemented.

REQ-L&D-12	List/display available training plan deployed from the server	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-L&D-13	List/display referenced system resource	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-L&D-14	List/display edge node dataset metadata	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-L&D-15	List/display/discovery dataset content	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-CD-16	Adding a new dataset	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-CD-17	Removing an existing dataset	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-18	Framework component deployment and uninstall	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-19	Framework component control with a CLI	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-20	Framework component control via API	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-21	Framework component configuration	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-22	Backup and restore	To implement through external tools
REQ-GI-23	Framework component log	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-24	Framework component audit	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-25	Framework component security	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-26	Framework AI/ML libraries support	Implemented
REQ-GI-27	Framework AI/ML differential privacy	Not directly. To be implemented.
REQ-GI-28	Framework AI/ML model agnostic	Implemented
REQ-GI-29	Framework AI/ML aggregation strategy	Implemented
REQ-E&M-30	Saving a model	Implemented

Fig. 20. Functionalities to be provided and related Flower status

These functionalities will be further described, designed and implemented in T4.2.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable is devoted to present the initial work done within WP4, focused on the definition and provision of the hybrid platform of the project. For doing so, a complete review of the use cases is presented, from which the main requirements related to the federated learning platform have been derived. Moreover, an initial description of this platform is provided, defining the main actors and modules to be developed and included, considering the hybrid approach that is needed. Finally, this document also contains an analysis of the state of the art of the main existing federated learning frameworks. Moreover, an identification of the evaluation criteria has been done, vital for the specific solution selection that will be used in the provision of the platform. Finally, a set of additional modules to be implemented on top of Flower is presented, which will be further designed and implemented in T4.2.

8 References

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